

Counter Responsibility and Accountability in Education Management

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Abstract

It is abundantly obvious that responsibility in education, which may be defined as being accountable to someone for the activities that take place in schools, is not a recent innovation. Since the beginning of time, it has been expected of teachers that they would stick to the curriculum that has been established for their classes, that they will maintain the organization of their classrooms, and that they will perform a range of additional obligations that involve but go beyond classroom education. Teachers were held accountable for their personal appearance (in the form of dress requirements) and behavior (both within and outside of the school environment), to an extent that is said to have been far more stringent than the many dress and ethical codes of conduct that are in existence today. Up until not so long ago, there existed a degree of responsibility equivalent to this one. As a direct consequence of these transitions, accountability regimes in schools have experienced considerable changes over the course of the previous three decades in terms of the structure of the regimes themselves, the breadth of their application, and the purpose they serve. Experimentation, innovation, and the willingness to take risks are circumstances that are essential for learning, but the prominence of these regimes in educational institutions has reached a point where they leave little to no opportunity for these activities. As school instructors answer (or respond to) yet another demand for "more responsibility," it is usual practice to perceive the source of the so-called "new burden" as being business. because they attribute the appeal for 'more accountability' to the world of business. Nevertheless, the business sector bears just a portion of the responsibility for the development of accountability practices. The testing procedure served as a model for human accounting, which was eventually adopted by the commercial sector, and

2

the training itself served as a model for the accounting itself. It is said by Hoskin (1996, page 268) that "the practices of writing, rating, and review were inventions of the educational world, not the business world." To be more specific, it was the very first method to apply numerical grading to written comments, and it was assessed in the year 1792. As a direct consequence of this, "a particular performance has become a record of a general truth," to quote Strathern (1997, page 307). In addition, the objectives were developed alongside the measurement, which means that "what happened clearly converges with what should be" The outcomes of individual students' performance on specialized examinations have, over the course of time, morphed into a measurement that is also used to assess the effectiveness of the institution. This development took place over the course of time. Although the notion of responsibility can be traced back too many forms of training, it has been modernized, institutionalized, and even reimagined within the context of today's current institutional structure.

Keywords: *Education Management, Manager Responsibilities , Accountability of Managers , Quality in Education Administration*

Introduction

According to Strathern, the term "cultural reproduction" describes the process by which "values move from one area of cultural life to another and then return again in modified form" (Strothern 1997, page 308). After being returned to the realm of education, the idea of accountability has gone through a process of steady growth and extension, and it has now become one of the most often debated themes among educators working in all contexts. Actually, many people would say that accountability regimes have extended to demonstrate that accountability is no longer just a component of the education system, but rather "constitutes the system" (Ranson 2003, page 459). At the very least in part, the necessity to demonstrate that government monies are being utilized on all fronts has contributed to the drive behind demands for "more accountable schools." As the strain on the public budget continues to increase, governments are increasingly connecting the financing of schools to the results of students' learning as a means of making these 'products' more available for consideration. This is a reaction to the reality that the expense of obtaining an education is continuing to go up. In other words, they are rendered calculable by using performance

CURRENT SCIENCE

metrics that have been specified by the government. Frequently, these performance metrics are linked to objectives that have been authorized by the government. These objectives may be summarized as gains in reading, numeracy, and citizenship; some examples of these results are increased study abilities; expansion of global markets; and increases in reading and numeracy. All these outcomes fall under government-approved policy. Computability mechanisms have been conceptualized by a variety of researchers, such as Corson (2002), Gale and Densmore (2003), Gewirtz (1999), Luke (2003), Meadmore (1999), Parry and O'Brien (2000), and Sachs (2003), among others. These researchers have established the foundation for the field. using the term "corporate managerial discourse" as part of an attempt to critique logic. The following criticism, which was written by Corson (2002), is representative of this kind of analysis in that it shows the detrimental influence of accountability by concentrating on accountability in the form of standardization, especially with respect to testing. This is one of the ways in which this sort of study may be characterized.

Education Governance Strategy

While we do not call into doubt the popularity of computability mechanisms as a strategy for educational governance, we are not too hopeful about designating a more complex collection of imperatives as an "ism" created by a monolithic neo-liberal state. While we do not call into question the prevalence of computability mechanisms as a strategy for educational governance. Instead, we put up the idea of risk in the shape of a "political and moral climate" (Giddens 2003) that compels schools to participate in a certain sort of performative work. To lessen the amount of personal, financial, and reputational risk that institutions of higher education are exposed to as a result of their activity, the institutions must make their activities calculable. To perform their roles as successful and "risk-conscious" school administrators, teachers and administrators need to keep their focus on "what is important" in the classroom and administration building. Because of this, they are required to both declare and define the aspects of education that are of value. It is both conceivable and important to quantify good order in the form of learning outcomes to show that the expense of education may be justifiably justified. Because of this, the emphasis that is now being placed is almost entirely on performance statistics. These data may be standardized via the use of benchmarking tools, which in turn enables outcomes to be compared on a local, state,

CURRENT SCIENCE

national, and international scale. In addition, there is a large demand among members of the public for school "league tables" that rank schools according to how well their pupils do on standardized examinations. According to Ranson (2003), annual charts provide a theoretical means by which governments, education authorities, parents, students, and the broader community may compare the performance of schools. The data used to compile these tables comes from students after they have completed their last year of schooling. Because of this, tables are useful as ways for making training apparent as both a positive and a negative component of the success of a business.

Consequences of Learning

It is possible to make the case that the consequences of effective teaching and learning are not fully represented in the league tables for some reason. The explanation for this is unknown. This is the case although some individuals have lauded league tables as a novel kind of 'transparency' made available to education clients. They are described to as "artifacts produced from a complex set of policy strategies and practical tactics that underpin performance production" by Ball (2001, page 221). Despite the ongoing discussion over the utility of these works, school administrators are being pushed toward teaching and learning techniques that maximize student accomplishment in the precise assessment tasks that form the foundation of their statistics. This is for reasons that are understandable since these practices enhance student achievement. Since they are directly impacted, they do not have the same luxury that other people enjoy, which is to discuss these topics from a more objective perspective.

Control Culture

What started with written and numerically scored assessments aimed to compare pupils individually, we now feel that a similar culture of supervision may be found in secondary schools, even though Strathern's study has concentrated on teaching institutions, which is what Strathern (1997) refers to as "supervision culture". A control culture is said to be made up of several different sets of assumptions, the vast majority of which are unconscious, as stated by McIntyre (2000). Because of intricate group dynamics that are impossible for us to completely comprehend, these presumptions have been ingrained in the thought processes of a great number of people. (McIntyre, 2000, page 1) (McIntyre, 2000) The culture of auditing reflects preconceived notions about what should and should not be taken into consideration, as well as what should and should not be

CURRENT SCIENCE

considered relevant. Schools are held responsible for their performance based on the degree of service that they deliver to their students. When it comes to determining the domains or domains of utmost significance for which schools will be held responsible in a culture that prioritizes control, stakeholders, including governments, governing bodies, parents, and students, are often engaged in the process. The current culture of control in schools places a high priority on measurable results such as a student's performance on standardized tests, the acquisition of skills in information and communication technology, and areas that frequently fall under the global definition of 'risk management,' such as child protection, student safety, and the safety of the workplace.

Health And Safety And Employee Relations, Outlined Earlier In This Document

At this juncture, it is important to emphasize once again that our position does not run counter to the fundamental principles behind the accountability or control concepts. The leaders of the school have an important part to play in ensuring that students, staff, and parents adhere to proper behavioral, safety, and educational standards. This involves having instructors who fulfill the necessary qualifications, having a solid physical infrastructure, and carefully organizing activities that include pupils to ensure that they not only satisfy educational standards but also safety standards. We are of the view that the enhanced accountability requirements in fields such as security are today undoubtedly contributing to an improvement in the degree of diligence and diligence in the activities that are being carried out, experiments and excursions. This is something that cannot be disputed.

Methodology

at spite of the fact that they now work at educational institutions, many teachers still have strong recollections of their time as students, when they "played" with mercury in the science lab by chasing small silver balls all over the lab bench. This activity was common. These potentially hazardous tasks have almost completely vanished from scientific labs in the contemporary world as a direct consequence of risk assessments, safety standards, and workplace health and safety regulations. It is abundantly evident that lecturers and school administrators, who are responsible for the creation and execution of adequate safety standards, will see a significant increase in their capacity to tighten laissez-faire educational norms as a direct result. However, because of

CURRENT SCIENCE

managers' attempts to define, measure, quantify, document, and report on certain aspects of duty, it's possible that their focus may shift away from their more general responsibilities. This is the region that we are interested in investigating further. Strathern (2000a; 2000b) and McIntyre (2000) have brought attention to characteristics of the supervisory culture that, in their opinion, have the potential to obstruct efforts to achieve great educational outcomes.

These elements were noted by Strathern (2000a; 2000b) and McIntyre (2000). As a result of the current emphasis that is placed on students' performance on standardized tests in many countries around the world, particularly in the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, and Australia, and the use of such results to measure school performance, many schools have made their efforts to put students on these standardized tests, relatively to the exclusion of other educational goals. This is especially true in countries like the United Kingdom, where the United States, Canada, and Australia place the most weight on students' performance on these tests. He started to put his attention on getting ready. Because of this, a lot of schools are now in a position where they are unable to fulfill the educational requirements of their pupils. This technique adheres to the tenet of Goodhart's Law, which states that "count counts."

Because of this, a great number of educational institutions have embraced a reductionist perspective of education that focuses on grades, market appeal, and the importance of the subject matter being taught. Even though educational programs and mission statements emphasize creativity, flexibility, and uniqueness, this is the situation that prevails. McIntyre (2000) will argue that success is synonymous with quantifiable outcomes, and that metrics are selected by governments based on objectives that were previously defined by their specific political interests. These goals may be outmoded at this point. This is consistent with the notion that success is connected to the achievement of quantifiable outcomes. In many instances, schools have evolved into closed systems in which daily activities are directed by externally-agreed-upon objectives.

Because of having an open system of reflective practice, almost all of the variation and breadth that was formerly accessible inside and across schools has been eliminated. A very crucial thing to ask is who precisely measures what and how they go about doing it. According to Strathern (2000a, page 4), audit culture also represents the premise that the performance of an organization

CURRENT SCIENCE

(such as a school or university) can be watched and assessed, and secondly, that performance may be made public and visible. Strathern states that this assumption is reflected in audit culture.

Strathern is quoted as saying that "control is transparency made permanent; it is also transparency made visible." These presumptions are based on the basic notion that openness fosters encouragement of constructive criticism and, as a result, leads to development. On the other hand, Strathern (2000a) and McIntyre (2000), along with several other researchers, have questioned whether an increase in the amount of information that is accessible results in an improvement or rather a better level of comprehension. Tsoukas (1994; 1997) is of the same opinion, pointing out yet another feasible risk. The danger is in the possibility that putting a focus on what could be just a small portion of the educational outcomes might lead to less attention being placed on other educational outcomes that might be just as essential or even more so. How essential is it that kids in our schools improve their social skills, that they become socially conscious, that they build connections with one another, and that they learn to collaborate well with others? There is a significant amount of rhetoric around these ideas, and it is often presented in terms of employability, citizenship or civic duty, and entrepreneurialism.

Although their implications are not considered when calculating high-stakes credentials, the tables for this section do not contain them. Even though schools collect important information such as reports, plans, lists, records, papers, and publications, and governments make sure that the necessary information is public accounting in some way, public accounting is still considered "real" labor. It is neglected to consider the institution's social structure, cultural values, and organizational structures (Strathern 2000a, page 4). This is since neither governments nor educational institutions are compelled to make information public. In this sense, the social is either fully emancipated from the systemic or absorbed into it, becoming a part of it. When quality is reduced to a number that can be computed, there is less room for assimilation or acceptance of data that is inconsistent or conflicting. Those who exist in the limbo between their duties and their responsibilities are not appreciated equally or equally.

Our argument is not that education "excludes" a "sense of social and moral vision," as Hargreaves and Goodson assert (see Sachs 2003, page xi). Rather, our contention is that education "includes"

CURRENT SCIENCE

such a sense. The formation of such values is now a significant job that is carried out as an important component of the contemporary progressive school's branding.

It is an essential component of the inclusive strategies and mission statements that are implemented in schools. As a part of their overall message, many schools utilize several promotional strategies in order to appeal to a larger proportion of the parent "market." These strategies generally place an emphasis on the significance of values, pastoral care, and a feeling of community in the educational experience.

When it comes to the day-to-day duty of monitoring school performance, these ambitions are continually challenged by continuous attempts to quantify the quality that we feel is vital to a culture of supervision. As a result, these ongoing efforts constantly threaten to reduce these aspirations down to the best, most hopeful rhetoric. The 'closed' system means that unexpected or unusual outcomes are not and cannot be examined; as a direct consequence of this, the experiment is either minimized or lost. This viewpoint is supported by research that was carried out in Australia by Lingard, Martino, Mills, and Bahr (2002) as well as research that was carried out in the United Kingdom by Gewirtz (1999).

The development of abilities like as critical thinking, autonomous thinking, and creative thinking, according to these academics, is only significant to the degree that it can be demonstrated that these talents lead to productivity as assessed by school test results. The loss of confidence, which is essential for the operation of most expert systems, also presents a potential danger. It is difficult to make all actions transparent, auditable, and accountable in an expert system that is as sophisticated as education since education is one of these systems.

Tsoukas (1997, p. 835) observes:

"Such practices [such as teaching] cannot be made completely transparent because there is no substitute for experiential and tacit knowledge, which is crucial to expertise and includes confidence in practitioners."

CURRENT SCIENCE

Because there is no way to replicate the kind of experienced and tacit knowledge that is essential to competence and relies on the faith of practitioners, this is the case. The language of accountability inhabits a distinct discursive space than the language of trust, which is highly significant for the teaching profession. The language of trust resides in a discursive space. This is since the imperatives of trust and improved understanding of risk are almost always incompatible with one another. In a study of local authorities in the United Kingdom that were required to report their results for a production index that was extremely narrowly focused, Tsoukas (1997) shown that quantitative performance indicators are not only counterproductive, but that they may also be downright absurd at times. The fact that these local authorities were compelled to submit their results formed the basis of the study that was conducted. It was expected that such results would serve as an incentive for local authorities to improve while also making them more open. One of these measures was the number of times home help personnel provided meals to elderly adults in their homes throughout the course of a certain time period. It is permissible for the local government to raise the quality of service merely by the number of visits made by home assistants rather than aiding the elderly at home directly.

As a consequence of this, it becomes better since more of a service that some seniors may not really desire is provided. Once criteria are supplied, Strathern (2000b) would argue, they settle in as the sole sign that is accessible, and common sense becomes a victim. In other words, indicators or performance measurements start to have a lifecycle of their own; they are self-sustaining as 'regime of truth' (Foucault 1980, page 131).

This is shown by the multiple factors for ranking that schools utilize in order to choose pupils to continue their education beyond high school. Strathern (2000a, page 2) asserts that the behaviors and practices that form the basis of such indicators are "taken out of context for the purpose of quantification." Few representatives of government, industry, or parent groups seem to be concerned with what pupils really know, fully comprehend, or are capable of doing. This is in stark contrast to their focus on children's social skills, cultural awareness, or concerns of justice. According to what was covered in the unit titled "Accountability, Responsibility, and School Leadership," when the score of a person is high, it is safe to assume that everything is going well. This one score is used to assess students, and in turn, schools, which can only reflect a tiny fraction

CURRENT SCIENCE

of the whole educational experience that schools deliver because of the nature of the score itself. Schools are rated and evaluated based on this one score. In their desire for an accountability system that provides verified and quantifiable outcomes in return for investment funds, governments have been influenced by an approach that is reductionist and linear. This strategy is based on the presumption that it is the only and best method, that 'best practice' can be recognized, defined, and quantified, and that the model will be a solution that is "one size fits all." This kind of model combines the essential 'quality control' accounting that is suitable for the production of goods like pharmaceuticals, airplanes, and computers, the need and desire to foster innovation and creativity, and suitable safeguards against the human irresponsibility, incompetence, and ignorance that can occur.

Higher Thinking and Problem Solving

For instance, the model may state something along the lines of "Quality control accounting is suitable for pharmaceutical, aircraft, and computer manufacturing." There is no one strategy that can successfully accomplish all of these many objectives all by itself. According to the reasoning that is presented by McIntyre (2000, page 3), "the most advanced skills and learning do not come from the imposition of control but rather from the ignition of interest." This resurgence of attention is partly attributable to components of specialized education systems that are less palpable and less susceptible to assessment. The 'pleasant clarity' of the culture of supervision (Barthes 1978), the knowledge, care, and passion of devoted staff members, the flexibility to adapt to the varied requirements of individual learners, and the development of both intrapersonal and interpersonal skills are essential.

Findings

In a twist of irony, a system that pretends to guarantee that school performance will be made more transparent, more public, and more responsible, and therefore more receptive to change, may in fact make such guarantees meaningless. According to Strathern (2000a, page 5), the language of assessment conceals many parts of the process that is involved in the development of the result, despite the fact that it claims to be a language that makes the outcome apparent. In addition, the discourse around transparency seems to obfuscate the act of concealing itself. The function of the principle, together with accountability and responsibility Because schools are complicated

CURRENT SCIENCE

institutions, the administrators in charge of them are faced with making judgments and selecting one suitable representation from a broad range of options. When making these judgments, the political and social environment in which the school functions, as well as the possibilities presented by that setting, are taken into consideration. They are "informed by the priorities, constraints, and climate set by the policy environment" (Ball 2001, p. 216), and this applies to both their internal and external operations.

As was said previously, accountability involves the concept of responsibility, either implicitly or overtly; as a consequence, it is intimately tied to problems with power, control, and authority. Formal accountability systems, which are used in a significant number of today's schools, place an emphasis not only on instrumental reflections of action but also on problems that are connected to the system as a whole. The demands of performance culture have led to the commercialization, marginalization, and eventual closure of the educational system's social, ethical, and moral aspects. Focusing on a genuinely extremely restricted repertory, as Ranson (2003, page 467) puts it, "may poorly represent [the school's] broader spiritual, cultural, moral, aesthetic, and intellectual values and aims."

In our view, the responsibilities that fall on school leaders extend much beyond the ambit of the official accountability structures that are already in place. It is vital to ensure that the beliefs, philosophies, and ideas described in mission statements, strategic plans, curriculum, and pedagogical frameworks are really put into practice day in and day out as a part of these responsibilities.

Daily Operations of Educational Institutions

The chances for school leaders to participate in ideas and principles such as social justice and fairness are diminishing as they are compelled to become more risk-aware and more performance-oriented in their roles. This is a result of the greater emphasis placed on the academic performance of students. Wrigley (2003, pages 89-90) issues a warning that if there is no opportunity for debate and criticism, "the urge to improve can easily become an acceleration in a cul-de-sac," which substitutes improvement with intensification. If there is no room for discussion and criticism, "the urge to improve can easily become an acceleration in a cul-de-sac." Because a greater focus is put

CURRENT SCIENCE

on the particular, the definite, and the evident, school leaders who foolishly embrace the principles that underpin the culture of control are likely to lose the capacity to deal with the social as well as the systemic. This is because more attention is given to the details. One of the abilities that we are gradually losing is the capability to concentrate on the intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and existential elements of learning to live in human societies. This is one of the talents that we are gradually losing. The issue of child safety is one that exemplifies how the reductionist effect of accountability may have a negative impact on the responsible conduct of teachers (Clarke 2001, page 30). Because of the inappropriate behavior of certain people in trusted positions inside schools, there has, quite correctly, been a proliferation of child safety regulations and procedures and an increase in the screening of workers working with children. These shifts are the direct outcome of improper behavior on the part of certain persons who were trusted in positions of authority. Some educational institutions have taken the position that the responsibility to preserve the safety of children should be read as mandating that personnel who come into close contact with pupils adhere to a "no-touch" policy. There is no question that these regulations satisfy the official accountability standards that are expected in this industry.

On the other side, one may argue that such an accountability system disregards the responsibility that schools have for the kids in their care to provide a welcoming and encouraging environment in which they can study. A friendly hand on the shoulder, a jubilant "high-five," or any other suitable sort of contact might be hard in terms of risk reduction and accountability norms; yet, they may really be the most responsible behavior. This is something that is alluded to by McWilliam and Sachs (2004). Other forms of physical contact that are acceptable include kissing, embracing, and holding hands. As was said previously, the formation of more formal systems of accountability in areas such as student safety has led to the implementation of essential reforms in specific areas of school practice (such as safety in labs); procedures led to the improvement of certain areas of school practice. Nevertheless, it is sad that the same rules might restrict what constitutes responsible and responsible conduct (such as appropriate touching).

From The Literature

The task that faces those in positions of authority is to ensure that the system of responsibility does not do away with the opportunities for responsible behavior. In addition, we will argue that the maximum amount of duty that can be allocated to school leaders and the highest level of responsibility that can be entrusted to school leaders are not the same thing. It is not the responsibility of school administrators to ensure that students have positive and pleasurable learning experiences or to create chances for instructors to address current political and social issues as a consequence of natural catastrophes. Neither of these responsibilities falls within the purview of school administrators.

They are not responsible for any of these matters at all. On the other hand, it is their duty to make certain that opportunities and experiences of this kind are made accessible to them. The leaders of the school are responsible for ensuring that the essential areas are maintained in order to make it feasible for elections to take place while the school is in session. The capacity of excellent teachers to adapt to the dynamics of the classroom, to enable students and themselves to experiment and take risks, should not be buried beneath the temptation to react simply to the obligations imposed by the system. This is because effective teachers have the ability to allow students and themselves to experiment and take chances. Accountability is an essential component of today's school leaders and administrators' professional toolkits and must be incorporated into all aspects of their work.

Argument

On the other hand, when accountability is the only leadership imperative, the imperative to engage with the social as well as the systemic can be overlooked. This review was carried out using the humanist paradigm (Creswell, 2007; Flick , 2006; Taylor & Bogdan , 1998; Strauss & Corbin , 1998) (Creswell, 2007; Flick , 2006; Taylor & Bogdan , 1998; Strauss & Corbin , 1998). The procedures used to collect data were focused group discussions (also known as FGD) and in-depth interviews. As part of the research project approach, we visited the university library and websites to explore relevant publications to explore issues related to the context of the study. Using the literature study as a basis, we explored a potential knowledge and practice gap in ethical leadership in the context of educational institutions. Aggressive and prescriptive ethics that underestimated

CURRENT SCIENCE

the socio-cultural dynamics of schools legitimized knowledge. As a result, its implementation seemed onerous and, to a greater extent, impractical for school principals. In a review of the relevant previous literature and an analysis of the codes of professional conduct enacted by the government and the teachers' professional association, the main issues that will guide this research are explored. Accepted practices, codes, contextual ethics and dialogue-based ethics are the concepts examined. As a qualitative researcher, I was aware that these core issues served as guidelines and that additional themes would emerge throughout the data generation process. We knew that other themes would develop in this process. In the process of collecting the necessary information for research, the concept of "personal thought" emerged. In the field research we conducted, I chose the school administrators as participants and we listened to their perspectives on the ethical problems that arise in their duties. We have also selected members of the School Management Committee (SMC), which includes both students and teachers, to develop and support the data obtained for this research. The selection has been deliberate (Patton, 1990) and the schools used are located in a particular region of Nepal, in the middle hill region.

Although I am an empathetic listener, there were times when I went deeper into certain lines of thought and/or definitions (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). After editing using the original recording, the transcribed data was encoded. To facilitate the process of creating themes, the coded data is grouped. The following categories were found to be important: policies, customs, contexts, personal considerations, and existing codes. The collected themes were then analyzed using a variety of theories (traditional, relational, contractual, collectivist, and communicative theories) in addition to my own personal reflections to explore the underlying meaning. Since relying on a single method would not be enough to maintain my credibility, we preferred to use several approaches instead (Creswell, 2003; Neuman, 2006; Cho & Trent, 2006).

The first method was called "member check" (Barbour, 2001) and it involved me bringing back the results so that the two school leaders who participated in my research could have a chance to critically evaluate and comment on the findings. (Creswell, 2007).

Second, an in-depth discussion and "triangulation" of data from my research participants (Patton, 1990) helped me better understand the situation in the field. Also, conversations with my field

CURRENT SCIENCE

assistant and insights from the theories helped me identify the meaning behind the facts. In addition, the detailed description of the experiences of the research participants, which I included both in my field notes and in my own thoughts, helped me acquire the meanings experienced within the framework of the study (Denzin , 1989; Ponterotto , 2006). This shows that the country's education policy is designed to involve school principals in general administrative responsibilities such as admission, transfer, record keeping, meeting, reporting, planning and budgeting, and to comply with the directives of their superiors.

Authority

On the other hand, when responsibility is the sole leadership objective, it is possible to miss the need of engaging with both the social and the structural aspects of the problem. This study was conducted with the humanist paradigm in mind (Creswell, 2007; Flick, 2006; Taylor & Bogdan, 1998; Strauss & Corbin, 1998) (Creswell, 2007; Flick, 2006; Taylor & Bogdan, 1998; Strauss & Corbin, 1998) (Creswell, 2007; Flick, 2006; Taylor & Bogdan, 1998; Strauss & Corbin, 1998). In-depth interviews and focus group discussions, often known as FGDs, were the methods that were used throughout the data collection process. As a step in the process of doing the research project, we went to the university library and other websites in order to read relevant publications and investigate problems that are pertinent to the context of the study. We investigated whether or not there is a possible knowledge and practice gap in ethical leadership within the setting of educational institutions by using the literature review as a foundation. The legitimization of knowledge was accomplished by the use of aggressive and prescriptive ethics, which grossly misjudged the socio-cultural dynamics of schools. As a direct consequence of this, its execution seemed burdensome and, to a larger degree, was not practically possible for school administrators. The primary concerns that will direct this investigation are dissected via an examination of the relevant prior literature as well as a study of the rules of professional behavior that have been adopted by both the government and the teachers' professional organization. The themes that are investigated include dialogue-based ethics, contextual ethics, accepted norms, and codes of ethics. As a qualitative researcher, I was aware that these fundamental concerns functioned as guides, and that more topics might emerge as the data collecting process progressed. In the course of this process, we were aware that more themes might emerge. The idea of "personal thought" came up

CURRENT SCIENCE

during the process of gathering the required material for the study. As participants in the field study that we carried out, I selected the school administrators, and we listened to their points of view on the ethical challenges that are presented by the responsibilities that they have. In addition, we have chosen members of the School Management Committee (SMC), which is comprised of both students and teachers, in order to develop and support the data that has been acquired for this study. The selection was done thus on purpose (Patton, 1990), and all of the schools that were used are situated in a certain area of Nepal known as the middle hill region.

In spite of the fact that I am a good listener, there have been occasions in which I have probed more into certain trains of thought and/or definitions (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Following the completion of the editing process with the primary recording, the transcribed data was encoded. The data that has been coded are organized in order to make the process of developing themes easier. Policies, conventions, settings, personal considerations, and existing norms were determined to be key categories. Personal concerns were also found to be relevant. After the themes were gathered, they were studied using a range of theories (including conventional, relational, contractual, collectivist, and communicative theories), in addition to my own personal thoughts, in order to investigate the deeper significance. Because depending on a single strategy would not be sufficient to maintain my credibility, we opted to make use of many strategies instead (Creswell, 2003; Neuman, 2006; Cho & Trent, 2006).

The first technique was referred to as the "member check" (Barbour, 2001), and it consisted of my bringing back the results so that the two school leaders who participated in my study could have the opportunity to critically assess and remark on the findings. This method was described in more detail in Barbour's article. (Creswell, 2007).

Second, a detailed conversation and the "triangulation" of data from the people who participated in my study allowed me have a better understanding of the situation in the field (Patton, 1990). In addition, discussions with my field assistant and insights gained from the theories were beneficial in assisting me in deciphering the significance of the evidence. In addition, I was able to acquire the meanings that were experienced inside the framework of the study with the assistance of the full description of the experiences that the research participants had, which I included both in my

field notes and in my own thoughts (Denzin, 1989; Ponterotto, 2006). I included this description in both of these places. This demonstrates that the education policy of the nation is structured to include school principals in general administrative activities such as admission, transfer, record keeping, meeting, reporting, planning, and budgeting, and to ensure that they comply with the orders of their superiors.

Ethical Practices of School Head Teachers

Factors Influencing Their Decisions

We were able to help school leaders better understand the aspects that play a key role in the ethical conduct of school principals via the dialogues, exchanges, and interviews I had with the persons who participated in the study.

The collected data at the study site revealed a number of recurring themes, some of which include traditional conceptions, policy requirements, individual perspectives, and the positions taken by the teachers' association. Conventional Philosophies and Values Every single responder shared the opinion that local traditions are relevant to the establishment of the ethical norms that are upheld in educational institutions. In addition to this, they said that the characteristics of a successful school leadership team include the demonstration of ethical behavior that is in line with the customs of the organization. One of the people surveyed is the president of the SMC. This participant claimed that despite the fact that the state has acceptable ethical regulations, these rules do not work in line with the traditions that are observed in the school. When decisions about schools are made at the national level, they might compromise the ethical conduct of school leaders by removing the seasoning of local culture that gives it a distinctive character. It is exceedingly difficult for school administrators to disregard local customs that have been handed down from generation to generation when it comes to following the ethical standards that are specified in the government's policy statement. People at the local level often choose to adhere to established cultural and social conventions that have been there for a long time. It is quite difficult for principals of schools to stand up to them. For instance, a teacher at the school where this study was carried out got married to a member of the "lower caste," who is also referred to as the "untouchable." As a consequence of this, he ran the danger of being disapproved of by the community. It is essential to have full faith in the assertion that the ethical choices that school

CURRENT SCIENCE

directors make are significantly influenced by the norms of the municipalities in which they work. He drew connections between the conventional notion of society and his own first-hand experience of "untouchability," which is a social construct that is still in use today. Going against the grain of tradition is not an easy task. Because the practice of immunity has been ingrained in the society for such a significant amount of time, it will be difficult to completely abolish it all at once.

Maintaining our operations in a manner that is consistent with our time-honored customs brings up yet another issue of concern. Because we are human, it is unavoidable that we will continue to act in the same manner as prior generations. As a consequence of this, the ethical practices of a new principal at a school have a high propensity to be comparable to the ethical practices of the principle who came before them.

This suggests that the conduct and performance of administrators are often impacted by the deeply ingrained history and culture of the institutions for which they are responsible. It is common for activities to take on a look that is unique to a particular school; hence, practices change from one school to another based on the atmosphere in which they are carried out.

[Related to the Neighborhood and Context](#)

The questions themselves constitute the immediate environment and backdrop that influences the ethical conduct of school leaders in both a direct and indirect fashion. Because the efforts of the community are widely deemed to be right, a school administrator cannot be in a position to publicly oppose such standards because of their authority. A principal at the school where I worked campaigned for a view that was quite similar to mine about the use of physical punishment. He said that the use of physical force against children was detrimental to their growth and that he did not want his school to use any kind of corporal punishment under any circumstance. Nevertheless, in his opinion, he is unable to sidestep the issue directly: It is quite challenging for us to put into practice the ethical principles that are outlined in the book. For instance, we wish to adhere to the recommendations made by child psychology, which state that we need to do all in our power to ensure the contentment of our offspring. The practice of spanking children should be discouraged since it may make them lose interest in the educational process. On the other hand, several people of our community have requested that the kids be disciplined in some form, and we cannot publicly

CURRENT SCIENCE

go against what they want. It's possible that the aforementioned idea is now considered archaic as a direct consequence of the prolonged campaign to dissuade the general public from supporting the practice of physical discipline. This demonstrates the challenge that school administrators confront when attempting to convince the community to quickly realize the implications of such behaviors, particularly given the degree to which such practices are established in society. Even some of the teaching staff at the school voiced some of the worries that were held by the pupils. A female teacher at the school that was polled has seen a situation quite similar to the one described above occurring in the area in which her school is situated.

"In this case, the parents stated that they believed that if their children were disciplined, then their children would accept the circumstances and not complain about them," All of these problems stem from their contexts. In certain instances, parents request that we discipline their children on their behalf so that their children would cooperate. Even if the regulation is in violation of the code of ethics, which prohibits such punishments in most cases, principals are expected to scrap it. They find it difficult to criticize these agreed-upon standards because they are ingrained in the context of the community that the school serves, which makes it difficult for them to challenge these goals that have been agreed upon. When it comes to matters of ethics, it might be challenging for school administrators to go against certain ethical standards of a community within a certain amount of time; as a consequence, principals are required to embrace the local context and norms of the culture in which they operate. The principals of schools often act as examples for the rest of the community. The findings of the survey revealed that the majority of participants felt that the faculty members were respected, which is exactly as it should be.

Conclusion

Nobody at the school seems to mind very much if the instructors don't do what they're supposed to do with their classrooms. There are situations in which teachers are unable to carry out their responsibilities, but the people of the community do not see this as a significant issue. Even while it was happening, community people disregarded and failed to see the gravity of the situation that had arisen. Even though it is abundantly evident that the state's code of conduct was broken in this scenario, not a single person of the community considers this breach to be a particularly significant

CURRENT SCIENCE

infraction of the regulations. The punishment for offences of this kind might in certain instances be fairly harsh. In conclusion, it is possible to assert that these rules of behavior are nothing more than the generally acknowledged ethical norms within the society. Individuals are led to conduct that is ethical by the beliefs and standards that they uphold. If educators took responsibility for their actions, there would be no need for intervention from the outside to develop norms and procedures that are ethically acceptable. According to the findings of the School Stewardship Committee, "principals are the right people to get school activities back on track." In spite of this, there are always going to be some circumstances that play a part in the development of unethical conduct among school administrators. However, there are certain key figures who are striving for change. This demonstrates that individual decision and reflection play essential roles in the setting in which this dialogue is taking place. When one individual or a group of people decides to make a change, it might open up a lot of doors to new opportunities that otherwise would not have been available. In addition, it is often acknowledged that a school administrator is a morally responsible someone who is able to supervise ethical issues. One female instructor has been quoted as saying that "the school principal is the person who plays the most important role in ensuring morality among the students and teachers in the school."

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